

FACULTY OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING
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MASTER'S THESIS

Adaptive Autonomy in Multi-Agent Systems with Modeled Interactions: An Empirical Analysis

Author	Athmajan Vivekananthan
Supervisor	Chathuranga Weeraddana
Second Examiner	Sumudu Samarakoon
Technical Advisor	Mehdi Bennis

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ABSTRACT

This thesis presents a decision-making framework for distributed systems where multiple autonomous agents operate in dynamic environments. The proposed approach integrates model predictive control with concepts from information theory and simulation-based planning. A key contribution is the development of a planning strategy that allows agents to make sequential or independent decisions while adapting for changing conditions of the environment in real time. The method handles systems with continuous state and action spaces and introduces mechanisms for dynamic agent prioritization, efficient use of computational resources, and robustness to inaccuracies in system models. Experimental results demonstrate that the method shows less vulnerability and scalability compared to traditional learning-based approaches when faced with changing conditions. These findings suggest that the proposed planning and coordination strategy is well-suited for online, scalable control in decentralized environments such as those found in large-scale sensor and actuator networks.

Keywords: Multi-agent systems, IoT, Model Predictive Control, Rollout Algorithms, Decentralized Planning, Adaptive Autonomy, Monte Carlo Simulation, Online Learning, Agent Coordination, Distributed Control.

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TIIVISTELMÄ

Tiivistelmä kirjoitetaan tähän. Tämä on diplomityöpohja, mutta sitä voidaan soveltaa myös kandidaatintöihin pienin muutoksin. Pohja soveltuu suomen- ja englanninkielisten opinnäytteiden tekemiseen.

Tämä tutkielma esittää päätöksentekomenetelmän hajautetuille järjestelmille, joissa useat autonomiset osajärjestelmät/agentit toimivat dynaamisissa ympäristöissä. Ehdotettu lähestymistapa yhdistää mallipohjaisen ennakoivan ohjauksen informaatioteorian käsitteisiin ja simulaatiopohjaiseen suunnitteluun. Tutkielman keskeinen tulos on suunnittelustrategia, joka mahdollistaa osajärjestelmien/agenttien tehdä päätöksiä joko peräkkäin tai itsenäisesti samalla, kun ne mukautuvat reaaliaikaisesti muuttuviin ympäristöolosuhteisiin. Menetelmä soveltuu järjestelmiin, joilla on jatkuvat tila- ja toimintatila-avaruudet. Se sisältää mekanismeja osajärjestelmien/agenttien dynaamiseen priorisointiin, laskentaresurssien tehokkaaseen hyödyntämiseen sekä järjestelmämallien epätarkkuuden sietoon. Kokeelliset tulokset osoittavat, että menetelmä on vähemmän haavoittuva ja paremmin skaalautuva kuin perinteiset oppimispohjaiset lähestymistavat muuttuviin olosuhteisiin sopeutuessa. Tulokset viittaavat siihen, että ehdotettu suunnittelu- ja koordinaatiostrategia soveltuu hyvin verkossa tapahtuvaan, skaalautuvaan ohjaukseen hajautetuissa ympäristöissä, kuten laajoissa sensori- ja toimilaitteiden verkoissa.

Avainsanat: Hajautetut järjestelmät, Internet-of-Things, Ennakoiva Mallipohjainen ohjaus, Rollout-algoritmit, Hajautettu suunnittelu, Adaptiivinen autonomia, Monte Carlo -simulointi, Verkkopohjainen oppiminen, Osajärjestelmien/agenttien koordinaatio, Hajautettu ohjaus

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FOREWORD

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Oulu, June 02, 2025

Athmajan Vivekananthan

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND SYMBOLS

AI	artificial intelligence
BP	base policy
CBL	case based learning
CBP	continual backpropagation
CRN	cognitive radio network
CTDE	centralized training with decentralized execution
DNN	deep neural network
DP	dynamic programming
DQN	deep Q-network
EC	edge computing
EV	electric vehicle
GIS	generalized importance sampling
IT-MPC	information theoretic model predictive control
IoT	internet of things
LA	look ahead
LLM	large language model
MA	multi-agent
MADDPG	multi-agent deep deterministic policy gradient
MADRL	multi-agent deep reinforcement learning
MARL	multi-agent reinforcement learning
MAS	multi-agent systems
MC	Monte Carlo
MCTS	Monte Carlo tree search
MDP	Markov decision process
ML	machine learning
MPPI	model predictive path integral
MPC	model predictive control
MPE	multi-particle environments
NN	neural network
PI	policy iteration
PPO	proximal policy optimization
RL	reinforcement learning
SA	single-agent
SOTA	state of the art
SP	signaling policy
VI	value iteration
$v_{k,i}$	perturbation added control action of trajectory i at time step k
W_{rew}	window size for moving average
π	sequence of policies
$\tilde{\pi}$	sequence of approximate policies
H	control sequence generated by a specified base policy
H^j	control sequence generated by a specified base policy of j^{th} agent
u^j	control decision of agent j
Δu	cost-weighted average of the sequence of trajectories
a_k^j	position of agent j at time k

\mathbf{b}_k^i	position of target i at time k
D	size of the training dataset
f_k	discrete time system dynamics at time k
g	time invariant stage cost
g_N	terminal cost function
$h(x_k, j)$	local heuristic q-factor of agent j at time step k
\mathcal{N}	normal distribution
$J^*(\mathbf{x}_0)$	optimal total cost of π
$J_\pi(\mathbf{x}_k)$	the total cost of π starting at \mathbf{x}_k
$J_N(\mathbf{x})$	optimal cost of the problem involving N stages
k	time index
\bar{k}	another time index
m	number of multi agents
M	number of trajectories
N_{mcts}	number of MC simulations
\mathbf{w}_k	random disturbance at time step k
\mathbb{E}	expectation
$O(\cdot)$	computational complexity order
p_w	probability distribution of noise
π_k	policy at time step k
π^*	optimal policy
μ^*	an optimal policy
q	cardinality of a local control space
R_k	reward at time k
$s_{i,\bar{k}}$	cost of the i^{th} from time index \bar{k} onward
Σ	covariance matrix
Σ^j	covariance matrix of j^{th} agent
\mathbf{x}_k	state at time step k
T^j	length of the horizon of agent j for BP_{roll}
\tilde{J}	approximate total cost
$\tilde{\mu}$	approximate policy
\mathcal{U}	finite control space
\mathcal{U}^j	control space of agent j
$\mathcal{U}_{\text{cont}}^j(\mathbf{x})$	continuous control space of agent j at state \mathbf{x}
$\mathcal{U}_{\text{dis}}^j(\mathbf{x})$	discrete control space of agent j at state \mathbf{x}
\mathcal{V}_k^j	sampled control trajectories of agent j at time k
$\hat{\mathbf{u}}^{\text{pre}(j)}$	an approximate vector of control ac of the preceding agents $i \in [j - 1]$
$\mathbf{u}^{\text{pre}(j)}$	vector of control ac of the preceding agents $i \in [j - 1]$
$\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{seq}}$	combined action after sequential decision making
$\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{aut}}$	combined action after autonomous decision making
$\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{succ}(j)}$	vector of control ac of the succeeding agents $i \in [m] \setminus [j]$
$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_k$	predicted value of random disturbance at time step k
$\hat{\mu}^j(\cdot)$	autonomous policy
$\tilde{\mu}^j$	approximate policy of agent j
\mathbf{u}_k	control input at time step k
\mathbf{u}^*	an optimal control
\mathcal{X}	state space
$\mathcal{X}_{\text{cont}}$	continuous state space

\mathcal{X}_{dis}	discrete state space
$\tilde{\mathcal{T}}$	set of uncaptured targets
BP	the base policy for discrete setting
BP _{mpc}	the base policy for information theoretic model predictive control (IT-MPC)
BP _{roll}	the base policy for rollout
ϵ_j	noise perturbation of agent j
\mathcal{D}^j	training dataset of agent j
Σ	covariance matrix
Σ^j	covariance matrix of j^{th} agent
γ	sensitivity threshold for reward
σ	an agent order
ϕ^j	neural network function of agent j
θ^j	parameters of the neural network of j^{th} agent

1 INTRODUCTION

In many applied fields, it is now commonplace to see numerous entities such as subsystems, agents, and cloud-based components working cooperatively to address multistage decision problems, often using control and machine learning algorithms trained on large datasets. In such settings, integrating mechanisms for planning and planning-driven online decision-making has become essential, as interconnected entities, from a broader perspective, need to effectively adjust their operations not only to enhance overall performance in real-time but also to adapt to system changes during the operations [1, § 8].

Multistage decision problems are predominantly formulated and solved within the mathematical framework of dynamic programming (DP) [2]. However, as the problem dimensionality increases, which is typical in problems within modern engineering applications, DP methods often become computationally intractable. In contrast, reinforcement learning (RL) offers solution approaches for determining optimal control policies by learning value functions over the state-space through trial-and-error interactions with the environment. As a result, RL has enabled the development of solution approaches for problems that were previously deemed computationally intractable using DP [1]. While RL-based policies are applicable to online decision-making, they do not effectively account for decision-time planning and adapting [1, § 8]. Nevertheless, such aspects are crucial in many engineering domains that inherently involve multi-agent (MA) settings with dynamic and adaptive environments with varying stressors. In this respect, algorithms enabling approximations in value-space with multistep look ahead (LA), such as rollout algorithms have emerged as an effective framework for seamlessly integrating adaptive and online decision-making with planning at each decision epoch [1, § 8.8], [3], extending beyond single-agent (SA) scenarios to MA settings [4]. However, the design of MA rollout algorithms for infinite control/state spaces has not yet been thoroughly explored, despite its significant relevance in emerging application domains with diverse problem settings. Additionally, the effects of varying rollout algorithmic parameters and their impact on engineering designs remain underexplored. Therefore, investigating these aspects is of critical importance.

1.1 Related work

Rollout algorithms present an appealing approach, exhibiting both practical effectiveness and theoretical soundness. From a practical perspective, they are particularly attractive due to their simplicity and ease of implementation, in contrast to state-of-the-art (SOTA) methods such as deep q-network (DQN) and policy gradient algorithms (e.g., TRPO, PPO, DDPG, and A2C), which often require extensive hyperparameter tuning and experimentation with various neural network (NN) architectures to achieve satisfactory performance on a given problem [5, § 1.6]. More specifically, at the current state, the action value is computed in real-time by first generating simulated trajectories, each initiated with a distinct possible action, followed by executing a predefined base policy (BP). The costs from these simulated trajectories are then averaged for each action, and the action yielding the largest expected return is selected. Additionally, rollout algorithms naturally lend themselves to efficient parallelization, as the simulation of trajectories under the BP can be executed independently in parallel. This characteristic significantly enhances their suitability for real-time decision-making applications. On the other hand, from a theoretical standpoint, rollout algorithms bear a strong resemblance to Newton steps in numerical optimization, providing an analytical framework to justify their reliability and convergence properties [5, § 1.5]. This connection further reinforces their robustness as a decision-making framework across a diverse application domains.

Applications of rollout algorithms include gaming [6, 7, 8, 9, 10], combinatorial scheduling algorithms [11, 12, 13], medical decision planning [14, 15], revenue management [16], disaster management [17], vehicle routing [18, 19], and robotics [20, 21], among others. Rollout algorithms for gaming have achieved superhuman-level performance, where they surpassed human experts in Chess, Go, Solitaire, and Jeopardy! [6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. It is worth noting that the state space of the related multistage decision problems of these algorithms are astronomical. Still the rollout algorithms enable real-time decision making and decision-time planning and adapting accordingly to the dynamic responses of the opponent.

Building on their success in strategic gameplay, rollout algorithms have emerged as a powerful tool in artificial intelligence (AI)-driven decision-making across diverse domains such as job scheduling, vehicle routing, logistics, and electric vehicle (EV) charging [11, 12, 13]. They are easy to implement and broadly applicable to complex, data-rich environments, where traditional heuristics often fall short. By combining simple heuristics with LA strategies, rollout methods enable dynamic reoptimization, consistently outperforming standalone heuristics in both average solution quality and worst-case performance. They reduce the gap to optimal solutions, compute feasible outcomes with minimal iterations, and have proven effective in tackling problems once considered intractable.

Rollout algorithms have shown strong impact in high-stakes domains like healthcare, revenue management, and disaster recovery [14, 15, 16]. In radiation therapy, they enable adaptive, overdose-aware planning where trial-and-error is impractical. In large-scale revenue management for airlines, hotels, and car rentals, rollout supports dynamic pricing and overbooking, handling disruptions without storing massive parameters. These fast, simulation-based techniques deliver guaranteed-quality solutions, scale to complex combinatorial problems, and enhance network-level resilience [17, 18, 19]. Such multistage sequential decision-making applications highlight rollout’s value in multi agent systems (MAS), particularly in situations where limited communication, such as in deep-sea or extraterrestrial collaborative missions that demand decentralized, adaptive planning in dynamic environments [22, 23, 24].

Given these promising applications of rollout in MAS, existing multi agent reinforcement learning (MARL) algorithms often underperform in complex, decentralized settings. Centralized controllers, though simple, create single points of failure and scale poorly [25]. Decentralized methods like independent Q-learning, centralized training with decentralized execution (CTDE), and value decomposition try to overcome this but face issues with non-stationarity, coordination, and scalability. Independent learners assume stationarity by modeling others as part of the environment, which fails in dynamic interactions [25, 26, 27, 28, 29]. Even advanced variants like Distributed Q-learning and DQN adaptations suffer from Q-value overestimation, catastrophic forgetting, and weak knowledge transfer, often requiring relearning from scratch [30]. Further, MARL methods are highly problem-specific, needing fine-tuning and handcrafted tweaks, which limits their generalizability and reliability [4].

In contrast, MA rollout offers a simulation-based, structured alternative that adapts naturally to uncertainty without fragile assumptions or reliance on replay buffers. It enables sequential, context-aware decision-making in real time. Unlike reward factorization methods, which struggle in environments with non-decomposable rewards like adversarial cognitive radio networks (CRNs), rollout evaluates contributions dynamically [30]. Actor-critic methods like multi-agent deep deterministic policy gradient (MADDPG) stabilize training using centralized critics but come with high computational overhead and low sample efficiency [31, 32]. Critically, relying on outdated experiences in replay buffers can lead to degraded performance in rapidly evolving settings. Rollout avoids these pitfalls, offering a scalable, robust, and generalizable framework for decentralized coordination in complex MAS scenarios.

While rollout algorithms have shown impressive results in discrete, SA sequential decision-

making, their extension to collaborative MAS especially in continuous control domains remains relatively underexplored. Most current efforts are confined to discrete action spaces, which limits their applicability to real-world robotics tasks that demand fine-grained, continuous control. In contrast, model predictive control (MPC) has long been the go-to framework for such settings, offering a well-established foundation rooted in classical control theory, with a strong emphasis on safety, stability, and constraint satisfaction [4]. However, conventional MPC approaches, particularly those based on gradient optimization, exhibit notable limitations. They typically require smooth cost functions for quadratic approximation, struggle to accommodate state constraints effectively, and often lack robust fallback mechanisms when no feasible trajectory is found.

Recent hybrid methods have begun bridging the gap between discrete planning and continuous control by mapping high-level discrete actions into low-level continuous commands [33], but these efforts are still sparse and problem-specific. This motivates the need for a more generalizable, sampling-based alternative that retains the adaptability of rollout while addressing the challenges of continuous, uncertain MAS environments. To this end, model predictive path integral (MPPI) control [34] offers a promising direction that circumvents the limitations of gradient-based methods by directly sampling control sequences, making no assumptions about smoothness or linearity in system dynamics or cost structures. It handles nonlinear dynamics naturally, accommodates soft constraints through large impulse cost terms, and gracefully manages infeasibility without requiring complex exception handling [35]. These properties make MPPI particularly well-suited for high-dimensional, real-time decision-making in decentralized, collaborative settings offering a principled framework that complements and extends traditional rollout approaches.

1.2 Contributions and organization of thesis

The contributions to the research problems from this thesis are threefold. First, MPPI is adopted for LA minimization, and a framework is developed for infinite state/control in multistage decision-making problems, which is then applied to sequential and autonomous MAS. Second, the utilization of agent ordering for achieving faster and better performance is explored. Third, the practical implementation of rollout algorithms in both finite and infinite control spaces is analyzed, with attention drawn to the fact that, despite the existence of many application specific variants, a systematic study of key algorithmic design trade-offs has been largely absent.

The organization of the rest of the thesis is structured as follows. Chapter 2 introduces the terminology, background, and foundational theory of multistage decision problems, with emphasis on DP, rollout algorithms, and their extension to MA settings. Chapter 3 presents the proposed rollout augmented information theoretic model predictive control (RAIT-MPC) algorithms, covering both sequential and autonomous coordination strategies, agent ordering schemes, and mechanisms for agents' adaptation when needed. Chapter 4 details the experimental setup and provides a comprehensive analysis of performance across multiple scenarios, including adaptive control under dynamic conditions and trade-offs in planning parameters. Chapter 5 concludes the thesis with a discussion about future research directions in intelligent internet of things (IoT) control systems.

2 TERMINOLOGY AND BACKGROUND

This section introduces the foundational concepts and notation used throughout the thesis. The section is presented by formulating the MA decision-making problem in the context of stochastic control and DP, drawing from the notation style of [36]. These preliminaries establish the mathematical basis for our rollout-augmented control framework.

Unless stated otherwise, vectors are denoted in boldface, while scalars appear in normal font. Scripted calligraphic symbols (e.g., \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{U}) denote sets or spaces such as the state-space or control-space. Temporal progression is indexed using subscripts, e.g., x_k denotes the system state at time step k . Moreover, superscripts are reserved for agent-specific indexing, e.g., u_k^j denotes the control input of agent j at time k . The joint control vector at time k , denoted \mathbf{u}_k , is obtained by concatenating u_k^j s for all j , i.e., $\mathbf{u}_k = [u_k^j]_j$. Superscript of indices within brackets is used to denote samples of a dataset. For example, $x^{(s)}$ is the s th sample in a dataset. A more detailed list of symbols and notation used is presented in the list of abbreviations and symbols.

The problem setting centers on infinite-horizon, discrete-time stochastic systems with decentralized control, where multiple agents collaboratively plan and act to minimize a cumulative cost. The presentation of problem statement starts with detailing the classical formulation of multistage decision problems, followed by a discussion of rollout algorithms as approximate dynamic programming methods. Then it is extended to the MA case, introducing sequential and autonomous coordination schemes that form the core of our proposed framework.

2.1 Multistage decision problems

An infinite-horizon discrete-time stochastic system that evolve according to

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = f(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{w}_k), \quad k = 0, 1, \dots \quad (1)$$

is considered, where k stands for the time index, \mathbf{x}_k is an element of some state space \mathcal{X} , the control \mathbf{u}_k is an element of some finite control space $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x}_k)$, and \mathbf{w}_k is a random disturbance with a given probability distribution p_w for all k that may depend only on \mathbf{x}_k and \mathbf{u}_k . A stage cost is incurred when applying control \mathbf{u}_k at state \mathbf{x}_k under disturbance \mathbf{w}_k , denoted as $g(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{w}_k)$.

The state-feedback control is defined as,

$$\mathbf{u}_k = \boldsymbol{\mu}_k(\mathbf{x}_k), \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_k$ is a policy that maps states to elements of the corresponding control space $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x}_k)$. Such a policy $\boldsymbol{\mu}_k$ is said to be admissible since $\boldsymbol{\mu}_k(\mathbf{x}_k) \in \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x}_k)$ for all k, \mathbf{x}_k . Given a sequence of policies $\boldsymbol{\pi} = (\boldsymbol{\mu}_0, \boldsymbol{\mu}_1, \dots)$, the total cost of $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ starting at \mathbf{x}_0 over infinite number of stages is given by,

$$J_{\boldsymbol{\pi}}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} g(\mathbf{x}_k, \boldsymbol{\mu}_k(\mathbf{x}_k), \mathbf{w}_k) \right]. \quad (3)$$

The expectation in (3) is computed with respect to the joint distribution of all the random variables $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N, \dots, \mathbf{w}_0, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{N-1}$.

The multistage decision problem involves minimizing the total cost function $J_{\boldsymbol{\pi}}(\mathbf{x}_0)$ over the policy sequence $\boldsymbol{\pi}$, where $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ belongs to the set of all admissible policy sequences [5, § 1.4]. This

represents a specific class of infinite-horizon multistage decision problems known as *stochastic shortest path problems*, where the objective is to reach a designated goal-state with minimal cost [5, p. 43]. Any goal-state incurs no cost, while all other states impose a strictly positive cost and should be avoided. Reaching a goal-state is assumed to be inevitable, effectively making the horizon finite. However, the horizon's length is stochastic and may depend on the chosen policy.

The standard solution method to compute an optimal policy π^* that minimizes the total cost $J_\pi(\mathbf{x}_0)$ and the corresponding optimal total cost $J^*(\mathbf{x}_0)$ is exact DP [2] that involves typically an iterative algorithm called *value iteration (VI)*. More specifically, let $J_N(\mathbf{x})$ be the optimal cost of the problem involving N stages, initial state \mathbf{x} , cost per stage $g(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w})$, and zero terminal cost. Thus, $J_N(\mathbf{x})$ is obtained after conducting N iterations of the form,

$$J_{k+1}(\mathbf{x}) = \min_{\mathbf{u} \in \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x})} \mathbb{E}[g(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w}) + J_k(f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w}))], \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, \quad (4)$$

which is known as the VI algorithm [2]. Note that the expectation in (4) is computed with respect to the distribution of \mathbf{w} . Under reasonable technical conditions, it can be shown that $J_N(\mathbf{x}) \rightarrow J^*(\mathbf{x})$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$ for all \mathbf{x} , where $J^*(\mathbf{x})$ is the optimal total cost with initial state \mathbf{x} . As a result of this limit together with (4) yields the well known Bellman's equations

$$J^*(\mathbf{x}) = \min_{\mathbf{u} \in \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x})} \mathbb{E}[g(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w}) + J^*(f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w}))] \quad \forall \mathbf{x}. \quad (5)$$

Moreover, let \mathbf{u}^* denote the control \mathbf{u} that minimizes the right hand side of (5) and define $\boldsymbol{\mu}^*(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{u}^*$ for all \mathbf{x} . Then it can be shown that the optimal policy is given by $\pi^* = (\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \dots)$ [2].

However, computing π^* using exact dynamic DP is generally intractable in practice. Furthermore, traditional DP methods are unsuitable for real-time decision-making in dynamically evolving environments, such as scenarios where \mathbf{w} changes over time. Consequently, approximate methods for solving (5) have become a practical necessity rather than a mere alternative.

2.2 Approximation in value space - rollout algorithms

There exist numerous variations of approximate solution methods [1, pp. 195-196]. However, the value-space approximation outlined in the remainder of this chapter is commonly referred to as one-step LA minimization or its multi-step variants [5, § 1.4.2]. These LA minimizations are pivoted around the right-hand side of (5).

In the case of one-step LA minimization, instead of J^* , we first use an approximation \tilde{J} . Then at any time epoch k and at any state \mathbf{x}_k , the control action $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}(\mathbf{x}_k)$ is determined by,

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{u} \in \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x}_k)} \mathbb{E}[g(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w}_k) + \tilde{J}(f(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w}_k))]. \quad (6)$$

Under appropriate conditions, this minimization results in a stationary policy $\tilde{\pi} = (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}, \dots)$ associated with the cost function $J_{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}}$ [5, § 1.4.2]. A particular computational approach to address the LA minimization is known as *rollout algorithms* [1, § 8.10] or *truncated rollout algorithms*, a more generalized variant, *c.f.* Fig. 1. They have been demonstrated to be instrumental in various contemporary machine learning (ML) algorithms that achieve human-level performance [3]. They are well-suited for *online decision-making* and *decision-time planning* [1, § 8.8]. Truncated rollout algorithms incorporate additional approximation techniques to compute $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}$, primarily during the expectation operations, calculation of \tilde{J} and the minimization stage [5, § 1.3.2]. Expectations are commonly approximated using Monte Carlo (MC) simulations. The calculation

Figure 1. Truncated rollout with multistep LA.

of \tilde{J} is performed by selecting an appropriate heuristic, known as the *base policy*, evaluating the corresponding returns through simulated trajectories of finite length followed by a terminal cost for stages beyond. Parametric cost approximations are widely used for the terminal cost estimations, e.g., NN trained on data. The approximation of the minimization operation typically depends on whether the problem involves a *finite* or *infinite* control/state space. In the case of *finite* control/state space problems, the methods for performing the minimization (approximately) involve computing action-value estimates using the previously mentioned expectation and \tilde{J} approximation techniques, and then selecting the action with the highest estimated value. In contrast, approximate mathematical optimization techniques must be carefully incorporated in the case of *infinite* control/state space problems.

The ℓ -step LA minimization is defined similarly to the one-step version. Fig. 1 shows a two-step LA tree. However, in this case, the optimization is carried out ℓ steps into the future, and the optimal action at the current time step is used when defining the policy $\tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{x}_k)$, more specifically by,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{u}_k \in \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x}_k)} \min_{\boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+1}, \dots, \boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+\ell-1}} \mathbb{E} & \left[g(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{w}_k) \right. \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^{\ell-1} g(\mathbf{x}_{k+j}, \boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+j}(\mathbf{x}_{k+j}), \mathbf{w}_{k+j}) \\ & \left. + \tilde{J}(f(\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell-1}, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}, \mathbf{w}_{k+\ell-1})) \right]. \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

It is important to note that the dynamics are linked via $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = f(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{w}_k)$ and

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+j} = f(\mathbf{x}_{k+j-1}, \boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+j-1}(\mathbf{x}_{k+j-1}), \mathbf{w}_{k+j-1}), \quad (8)$$

for all $j = 2, \dots, \ell - 1$ within (7). The approximation stages of ℓ -step LA are the same as those in one-step LA minimization. However, the associated trade-offs become critical in practice when these algorithms are deployed in real-world environments [1, § 8.10].

2.3 Extensions to MA case

Value-space approximations utilizing rollout algorithms can be naturally extended to incorporate MA settings within multistage decision problems [4][5, § 2.9]. In particular, for a system with m agents, the control space $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x})$ at any state \mathbf{x} is assumed to be the Cartesian product of m local control-spaces, i.e.,

$$\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{U}^1(\mathbf{x}) \times \dots \times \mathcal{U}^j(\mathbf{x}) \times \dots \times \mathcal{U}^m(\mathbf{x}) \quad \forall \mathbf{x}. \quad (9)$$

where $\mathcal{U}^j(\mathbf{x})$ corresponds to the control space of agent j . Consequently, the control action \mathbf{u} is composed of m individual components, \mathbf{u}^j for $j = 1, \dots, m$, where each $\mathbf{u}^j \in \mathcal{U}^j(\mathbf{x})$ corresponds to the control decision of a specific agent at state \mathbf{x} , resulting in $\mathbf{u} = [\mathbf{u}^1, \dots, \mathbf{u}^m] \in \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x})$.

The aforementioned structure of the control-space facilitates the development of efficient and reliable algorithms for computing stationary policies in MASs, which would otherwise require an overwhelming computational effort. For instance, in a finite control-space problem where $|\mathcal{U}^j(\mathbf{x})| = q$ for all agents j and states \mathbf{x} , the computational complexity is reduced from $O(q^m)$ to $O(qm)$ [4]. The class of such algorithms are known as *sequential MA rollout* (or agent-by-agent rollout) which offers strong performance guarantees under appropriate conditions [4].

2.4 Sequential MA rollout

In this section, only the one-step LA approach is presented while the extension to the multi-step case follows analogously [4, § IV-A]. The key mechanism underpinning the sequential MA rollout is alternating optimization [37]. More specifically, given a fixed ordering of $[m] \triangleq \{1, \dots, m\}$, the minimization operation in (6) sequentially iterates through each index j , optimizing over the corresponding variable \mathbf{u}^j at each step.

For clarity, consider the case where the ordering follows $[m]$ itself, i.e., in its natural sequence¹. Under this setup, each agent $j \in [m]$ yields its policy $\tilde{\mu}^j(\mathbf{x}_k)$ from,

$$\tilde{\mu}^j(\mathbf{x}_k) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{u}^j \in \mathcal{U}^j(\mathbf{x}_k)} \mathbb{E} \left[g(\mathbf{x}_k, (\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{pre}(j)}, \mathbf{u}^j, \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{succ}(j)}), \mathbf{w}_k) + \tilde{J} \left(f(\mathbf{x}_k, (\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{pre}(j)}, \mathbf{u}^j, \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{succ}(j)}), \mathbf{w}_k) \right) \right]. \quad (10)$$

It is important to note that when each agent $j \in [m]$ solves (10), two additional problem parameters, namely $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{pre}(j)}$ and $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{succ}(j)}$, must be known beforehand. In particular, $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{pre}(j)}$ is the vector of policies of the preceding agents $i \in [j-1]$, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{pre}(j)} = (\tilde{\mu}^1(\mathbf{x}_k), \dots, \tilde{\mu}^{j-1}(\mathbf{x}_k)). \quad (11)$$

Accordingly, it is assumed that a coordination mechanism is in place to facilitate intercommunication from all $i \in [j-1]$ to agent j . On the other hand, $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{succ}(j)}$ is the vector of an appropriately chosen BPs $\mu^i(\mathbf{x}_k)$ of the succeeding agents $i \in [m] \setminus [j]$, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{succ}(j)} = (\mu^{j+1}(\mathbf{x}_k), \dots, \mu^m(\mathbf{x}_k)). \quad (12)$$

Additional approximation techniques are employed in the online implementation of the minimization in (10), similar to those outlined in (6).

2.5 Autonomous MA rollout

Recall that each agent j requires the control $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{pre}(j)}$ of preceding agents to determine its decision $\tilde{\mu}^j(\mathbf{x}_k)$ as per (10). In contrast, autonomous MA rollout utilizes past decision experiences

¹Generalizations are discussed in our algorithms presented in § 3.

to model $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}^i(\mathbf{x}_k)$ for preceding agents $i \in [j - 1]$ using data-driven methods such as NNs. Specifically, for each agent $j \in [m]$, a NN is trained to output $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{pre}(j)}$, an approximate of $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{pre}(j)}$, based on training data pairs $(\mathbf{x}^{(s)}, \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}^{(s)}}^{\text{pre}(j)})$ for $s = 1, \dots, S$. Consequently, the output $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{pre}(j)}$ of the NN is used for computing the autonomous policy $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}^j(\mathbf{x}_k)$ given by,

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}^j(\mathbf{x}_k) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{u}^j \in \mathcal{U}^j(\mathbf{x}_k)} \mathbb{E} \left[g(\mathbf{x}_k, (\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{pre}(j)}, \mathbf{u}^j, \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{succ}(j)}), \mathbf{w}_k) + \tilde{J}(f(\mathbf{x}_k, (\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{pre}(j)}, \mathbf{u}^j, \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_k}^{\text{succ}(j)}), \mathbf{w}_k)) \right]. \quad (13)$$

Autonomous MA rollout (13), in contrast to its sequential counterpart (10), enables efficient parallelized decision-making by eliminating the necessity for inter-agent communication.

3 METHODOLOGY

A novel algorithm has been proposed in this chapter for addressing multistage MA decision problems in continuous (infinite) control/state spaces. Broadly, the algorithms are centered on integrating MA rollout framework with approximate solution methods for stochastic optimal control, formulated within the *information theoretic model predictive control (IT-MPC)* framework [35], which is shown to have close technical relations to the MPPI under restricted conditions [34]. Subsequently, it is demonstrated how agent ordering can be seamlessly incorporated into MA rollout algorithms to enhance performance, followed by the development of computationally efficient variants that are well-suited for online decision-making with integrated decision-time planning.

3.1 Certainty-equivalent MPC for rollouts: Caveats

Let us start by considering a SA case with classic certainty equivalent MPC. In this case, the resulting MPC formulation that is viewed as an approximation in value space with ℓ -step LA minimization (7), is given by

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize} && \sum_{j=k}^{k+\ell-1} g(\mathbf{x}_j, \mathbf{u}_j, \hat{\mathbf{w}}_j) + \tilde{J}(\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell}) \\ & \text{subject to} && \mathbf{x}_{j+1} = f(\mathbf{x}_j, \mathbf{u}_j, \hat{\mathbf{w}}_j), \quad j = k, \dots, k + \ell - 1 \\ & && \mathbf{u}_j \in \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x}_j), \quad j = k, \dots, k + \ell - 1, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where the variables are controls $(\mathbf{u}_k, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1})$ and states $(\mathbf{x}_{k+1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{k+\ell})$. It is worth noting that the \mathbf{w}_k is replaced with $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_k$, which is a predicted value of the former.

However, directly addressing MPC formulation (14) typically requires solving nonlinear programming problems using algorithms such as sequential quadratic programming [38]. In addition to control constraints, multistage decision problems involving continuous state and control spaces often incorporate state constraints. While such constraints can be encoded into the cost functions g and \tilde{J} using non-smooth functions such as the indicator function, this approach compromises the smoothness of the overall cost function, thereby limiting the applicability of conventional solvers relying on sequential quadratic programming. Alternatively, state constraints can be handled separately using more general methods based on sequential convex programming [37]. Nevertheless, MPC formulations of the form (14) may still result in infeasible optimization problems, especially in real-time applications, thus requiring auxiliary mechanisms to address feasibility issues online. Last but not least, the functions g , f , and \tilde{J} are not available in closed form in nearly all multistage decision problems emerging across diverse application domains [3, 4, 5]. Therefore, standard mathematical optimization solvers are generally inapplicable to solving certainty-equivalent MPC, making such formulations less promising for integration with rollout algorithms.

Accordingly, the proposed rollout algorithms are developed based on IT-MPC [35], which circumvents the limitations inherent to certainty-equivalent MPC formulation (14). The characteristics of IT-MPC provide a sampling-based control framework that is conveniently amenable to integration with the rollout algorithms, as will be discussed in the sequel.

3.2 RAIT-MPC

To formally present the the IT-MPC formulation to build the proposed subsequent rollout algorithms, it is useful to introduced some notations which are not originally present in the

ℓ -step LA minimization (7). It is assumed that there is no direct control available over the input of the dynamical system (1). Instead, over each finite horizon of length ℓ , the nominal input $\mathbf{u}_k, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}$, for which the control defined above, is subject to additive Gaussian noise with known characteristics. More specifically, each control \mathbf{u}_j is perturbed by a noise term $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_j \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$, resulting in the actual control applied to the system being $(\mathbf{u}_j + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_j)$. Under this assumption, IT-MPC formulated by,

$$\underset{(\mathbf{u}_k, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1})}{\text{minimize}} \mathbb{E}_{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{w}} \left[\sum_{j=k}^{k+\ell-1} g(\mathbf{x}_j, \mathbf{u}_j + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_j, \mathbf{w}_j) + \tilde{J}(\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell}) \right]. \quad (15)$$

This yields that, for a given current state \mathbf{x}_k , the solution to the IT-MPC (15) characterizes a control trajectory of length ℓ that minimizes the expected cost across sampled realizations of the system dynamics.

Under more specific conditions, it has been shown in the IT-MPC literature that the notion of optimality of (15) coincides with that of the stochastic optimal control [35, § IV]. More importantly, the solution is approximated by a sampling based schemes precluding the need for optimization solvers [35, Algorithm 1]. The principle of the sampling based solution within the context of (15) involves the following key steps. First the algorithm generates a sequences of sampled control trajectories,

$$\mathcal{V}_k = \{(\mathbf{v}_{k,i}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{k+\ell-1,i})\}_{i \in [M]}, \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_{t,i} = \mathbf{u}_t + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{t,i}$ for all t and i with $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{t,i}$ drawn from the distribution $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$ and $(\mathbf{u}_k, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1})$ being an ℓ step trajectory from an adequate BP. Second, the cost of the i th trajectory from time index \bar{k} onward, denoted $s_{i,\bar{k}}$, is computed. In particular, associated with each control trajectory $i \in [M]$ and its time index $\bar{k} \in \{k, \dots, k + \ell - 1\}$, $s_{i,\bar{k}}$ is computed by

$$s_{i,\bar{k}} = \sum_{t=\bar{k}}^{k+\ell-1} g(\mathbf{x}_{t,i}, \mathbf{v}_{t,i}, \mathbf{w}_{t,i}) + \tilde{J}(\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell,i}), \quad (17)$$

where for all $i \in [M]$, $\mathbf{x}_{k,i} = \mathbf{x}_k$, $\mathbf{w}_{t,i}$ is drawn according to the distribution $p_{\mathbf{w}}$, and for all control trajectory $i \in [M]$, time index $t \in \{k + 1, \dots, k + \ell\}$, $\mathbf{x}_{t,i}$ is the state landed according to (1). Finally, an approximate solution for (15), denoted $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+\ell-1})$ is computed as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_t = \mathbf{u}_t + \Delta \mathbf{u}_t, \quad t = k, \dots, k + \ell - 1, \quad (18)$$

where $\Delta \mathbf{u}_t$ is a cost-weighted average of the sequence of trajectories given by

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_t = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M \exp(-(1/\lambda)s_{i,t}) \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{t,i}}{\sum_{i=1}^M \exp(-(1/\lambda)s_{i,t})}, \quad (19)$$

and λ is a positive scalar. The first control input $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k$ is applied to the system, while the remaining controls define the mean of the distribution used for sampling in the subsequent time index $k + 1$.

Building upon the preceding discussion, the proposed RAIT-MPC algorithm is outlined here. For brevity, introduction of the notation $H(p_{\mathbf{w}}, \text{BP}, f, \ell; \mathbf{x}_j)$ is presented to denote the control sequence generated by a specified base policy BP over ℓ stages, starting from state \mathbf{x}_j and evolving according to the system dynamics f , with disturbances at each stage sampled from the distribution $p_{\mathbf{w}}$.

Algorithm 1 outlines the core steps of the RAIT-MPC framework of a single agent, (extended to MAS subsequently in *c.f.* § (3.3)) with infinite state and control spaces. At each time step

Algorithm 1 RAIT-MPC

- 1: **Given:** \mathbf{x}_0 , initial state; M , number of sampled trajectories; ℓ , number of multistages; p_w , disturbance distribution, f , transition model, Σ , noise covariance; BP_{mpc} , the base policy for IT-MPC; BP_{roll} , the base policy for rollout; T , length of the horizon for BP_{roll} .
- 2: $k = 0$
- 3: **while** Task is not completed **do**
- 4: current state = \mathbf{x}_k
- 5: $(\mathbf{u}_k, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}) = H(p_w, \text{BP}_{\text{mpc}}, f, \ell; \mathbf{x}_k)$
- 6: Compute \mathcal{V}_k from (16)
- 7: For each trajectory $i \in [M]$, compute $\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell,i}$ and the rollout base policy controls for T stages, i.e., $(\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell,i}, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell+T-1,i}) = H(p_w, \text{BP}_{\text{roll}}, f, T; \mathbf{x}_{k+\ell,i})$
- 8: For each trajectory $i \in [M]$, compute rollout base policy cost denoted by c_i , where

$$c_i = \sum_{t=k+\ell}^{k+\ell+T-1} g(\mathbf{x}_{t,i}, \mathbf{u}_{t,i}, \mathbf{w}_{t,i}) \quad (20)$$

- 9: For each $i \in [M]$, let $\tilde{J}(\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell,i}) = c_i + d_i$ where d_i is the terminal cost at $\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell+T,i}$
 - 10: Compute $s_{i,\bar{k}}$ from (17)
 - 11: Compute $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+\ell-1})$ from (18)
 - 12: Observe \mathbf{w}_k from the environment and pick $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k$ to move to \mathbf{x}_{k+1} according to (1)
 - 13: $k = k + 1$
 - 14: **end while**
-

k , a nominal control sequence is generated using the base policy BP_{mpc} and perturbed with Gaussian noise to create M sampled trajectories \mathcal{V}_k . The resulting post-horizon states $\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell,i}$ are then evaluated using a T -step rollout with base policy BP_{roll} . The associated rollout and terminal costs define the surrogate cost-to-go $\tilde{J}(\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell,i})$, used to update trajectory costs via (17). These trajectory costs are then used in an importance-weighted update (18) to shift the control sequence $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+\ell-1})$ toward lower-cost actions. The updated sequence also defines the sampling mean for the next iteration. This sampling-based approach bypasses direct nonlinear optimization, enabling iterative refinement of control decisions through statistical inference in complex, uncertain environments.

3.3 MA-sequential rollout augmented information theoretic model predictive control (S-RAIT-MPC)

It is important to note that Algorithm 1 represents the integration of IT-MPC with an ℓ -step LA with rollout techniques [c.f. § 2.2]. In a similar manner, IT-MPC can also be combined with sequential MA ℓ -step LA with rollouts [c.f. § 2.4], which is discussed in the sequel.

Recall the minimization operation in the sequential MA rollout is performed by fixing an order $[m]$ and optimizing through each agent's control variable \mathbf{u}^j according to the order, c.f. § 2.4. Here, the goal is to formulate an agent-centric IT-MPC problem. To this end, a nominal input is considered, $\mathbf{u}_k, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}$ of length ℓ , where for each $j \in [m]$, \mathbf{u}_t is partitioned as

$$\mathbf{u}_t = (\mathbf{u}_t^{\text{pre}(j)}, \mathbf{u}_t^j, \mathbf{u}_t^{\text{succ}(j)}), \quad t = k, \dots, k + \ell - 1. \quad (21)$$

From the point of view of agent j , $\mathbf{u}_t^{\text{pre}(j)}$ and $\mathbf{u}_t^{\text{succ}(j)}$ are *known* problem parameters and represent the preceding and succeeding agents' controls, respectively. Only the decision \mathbf{u}_t^j is

Figure 2. MA-S-RAIT-MPC with $m = 3$. Each proceeding agents' computed control action is communicated to the successive agents as marked with orange lines.

at the disposal of agent j and is perturbed by a noise term $\epsilon_t^j \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \Sigma^j)$. As a result, for $t = k, \dots, k + \ell - 1$, the actual control, denoted $\mathbf{u}_t(\mathbf{u}_t^j, \epsilon_t^j)$, applied to the system is

$$\mathbf{u}_t(\mathbf{u}_t^j, \epsilon_t^j) = (\mathbf{u}_t^{\text{pre}(j)}, \mathbf{u}_t^j + \epsilon_t^j, \mathbf{u}_t^{\text{succ}(j)}) \quad (22)$$

and consequently, the j th agent-centric IT-MPC problem formulation is given by

$$\underset{(\mathbf{u}_k^j, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}^j)}{\text{minimize}} \mathbb{E}_{\epsilon^j} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{w}} \left[\sum_{t=k}^{k+\ell-1} g(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t(\mathbf{u}_t^j, \epsilon_t^j), \mathbf{w}_t) + \tilde{J}^j(\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell}) \right]. \quad (23)$$

The principle of the sampling based solution [35, Algorithm 1] can be incorporated to yield a solution method to problem (23) by suitably modifying (16)-(19). In particular, instead of \mathcal{V}_k^j in (16), each agent $j \in [m]$ now maintains an own sequence of M^j sampled control trajectories, denoted by \mathcal{V}_k^j , and defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{V}_k^j = \{(\mathbf{v}_{k,i}^j, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{k+\ell-1,i}^j)\}_{i \in [M^j]}, \quad (24)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_{t,i}^j = \mathbf{u}_t + \bar{\epsilon}_{t,i}^j$ for all t and i and $(\mathbf{u}_k, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1})$ is a given nominal vector. More importantly, $\bar{\epsilon}_{t,i}^j$ is a vector composed of m blocks, where all blocks except the j th are identically zero, and the j th block is given by $\epsilon_{t,i}^j$, sampled from the distribution $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \Sigma^j)$, i.e.,

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{t,i}^j = (\underbrace{\mathbf{0}, \dots, \mathbf{0}}_{j-1 \text{ blocks}}, \epsilon_{t,i}^j, \underbrace{\mathbf{0}, \dots, \mathbf{0}}_{m-j \text{ blocks}}). \quad (25)$$

Equations (24) and (25) indicate that, in contrast to the formulation in (16), the noise perturbations to the sampled control trajectories are introduced solely by agent j . Next, in place of (17), an

Algorithm 2 MA-S-RAIT-MPC

- 1: **Given:** \mathbf{x}_0 , initial state; M^j , number of sampled trajectories of agent j ; ℓ , number of multistages; p_w , disturbance distribution; f , transition model; Σ^j , noise covariance for agent j ; BP_{mpc} , the base policy for IT-MPC; BP_{roll} , the base policy for rollout; T^j , length of the horizon for BP_{roll} at agent j .
 - 2: $k = 0$
 - 3: **while** Task is not completed **do**
 - 4: current state = \mathbf{x}_k ; $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_k^{\text{pre}(1)} = \emptyset$; $\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{seq}} = \emptyset$
 - 5: **for** each agent $j \in [M]$ **do**
 - 6: Receive preceding agents' controls $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_k^{\text{pre}(j)}$
 - 7: $(\mathbf{u}_k, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1}) = H^j(p_w, \text{BP}_{\text{mpc}}, f, \ell; \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k^{\text{pre}(j)} = \bar{\mathbf{u}}_k^{\text{pre}(j)})$
 - 8: Compute \mathcal{V}_k^j from (24)
 - 9: For each trajectory $i \in [M^j]$, compute $\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell,i}$ and the rollout base policy controls for T^j stages, i.e., $(\mathbf{u}_{k+\ell,i}, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell+T-1,i}) = H(p_w, \text{BP}_{\text{roll}}, f, T^j; \mathbf{x}_{k+\ell,i})$
 - 10: For each trajectory $i \in [M^j]$ compute rollout base policy cost denoted by c_i , where

$$c_i = \sum_{t=k+\ell}^{k+\ell+T-1} g(\mathbf{x}_{t,i}, \mathbf{u}_{t,i}, \mathbf{w}_{t,i}) \quad (27)$$
 - 11: For each $i \in [M^j]$, let $\tilde{J}^j(\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell,i}) = c_i + d_i$ where d_i is the terminal cost at $\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell+T,i}$
 - 12: Compute $s_{i,\bar{k}}^j$ from (26)
 - 13: Compute $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+\ell-1})$ from (18) by substituting $s_{i,t}^j, \bar{\epsilon}_{t,i}^j$ in (19)
 - 14: Perform block extraction to yield $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k^j, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+\ell-1}^j)$
 - 15: $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_k^{\text{pre}(j+1)} \leftarrow (\bar{\mathbf{u}}_k^{\text{pre}(j)}, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k^j)$; $\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{seq}} \leftarrow (\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{seq}}, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k^j)$
 - 16: **end for**
 - 17: **return**
 - 18: Observe \mathbf{w}_k from the environment and pick $\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{seq}}$ to move to \mathbf{x}_{k+1} according to (1)
 - 19: $k = k + 1$
 - 20: **end while**
-

agent-specific trajectory cost $s_{i,\bar{k}}^j$ is computed in an analogous manner. Specifically, for each agent $j \in [m]$, control trajectory $i \in [M^j]$ and its time index $\bar{k} \in \{k, \dots, k + \ell - 1\}$, $s_{i,\bar{k}}^j$ is computed by

$$s_{i,\bar{k}}^j = \sum_{t=\bar{k}}^{k+\ell-1} g(\mathbf{x}_{t,i}, \mathbf{v}_{t,i}^j, \mathbf{w}_{t,i}) + \tilde{J}^j(\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell,i}). \quad (26)$$

Consequently, $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+\ell-1})$ is computed according to (18) by replacing $s_{i,t}$ and $\epsilon_{t,i}$ in (19) by $s_{i,t}^j$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_{t,i}^j$, respectively. Finally, the approximate solution of (23), denoted $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k^j, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+\ell-1}^j)$, is computed from $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+\ell-1})$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_t^j$ is the j th block of $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_t$. The extraction of j th block from $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_t$ is referred to as *block extraction* and is denoted by the operator $\text{Block}_j(\cdot)$ where $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_t^j = \text{Block}_j(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_t)$. The first control input $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k^j$ is scheduled to be applied to the system, while the remaining controls define the mean of the distribution used for sampling in the subsequent time index $k + 1$.

The steps of the preceding discussion is integrated in an iterative manner with an agent order specified by the identity permutation σ_{id} of $[m]$. As such, steps for MA-S-RAIT-MPC are given in Algorithm 2. The central idea is to solve each agent's control problem one after another in

Figure 3. MA-A-RAIT-MPC with $m = 3$. Successive agents do not have to wait until preceding agents communicate their actions. Instead they predict them with a learned model of predecessors.

a fixed order, enabling a structured coordination mechanism. At each time step k , each agent j computes its own nominal control sequence $(\mathbf{u}_k, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{k+\ell-1})$ by using BP_{mpc} , see step 7 of Algorithm 2. When doing so, it is assumed that the exact control of the preceding agents $\mathbf{u}_t^{\text{pre}(j)}$ for $t = k$ is available at agent j and \mathbf{u}_k is updated accordingly. The corresponding computation is compactly represented by the operator H^j . For each agent $j \in [m]$, the control sequence is partitioned as per (21) into three parts: the controls of preceding agents, the current agent's control, and the controls of succeeding agents. Only the current agent's control is perturbed with Gaussian noise as per (22), while the other parts remain fixed. This results in a set of perturbed trajectories for that agent. For each trajectory, the values of states that come after the planning horizon (after time $k + \ell$) is evaluated using a separate rollout procedure of length T^j governed under BP_{roll} . The cumulative cost of the rollout computed using (26), plus any terminal cost forms the *surrogate cost-to-go*, which is used to compute a cost-weighted update of the agent's control using importance sampling similar to explanation in Algorithm 1. After each agent optimizes the joint control sequence, its own control trajectory is extracted and the very first component of the trajectory is passed along to the next agent in the sequence and also stored in $\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{seq}}$, generated by the joint action merger (JAM), to be applied to the system to transition to the next state \mathbf{x}_{k+1} , c.f. Fig. 2.

3.4 MA-autonomous rollout augmented information theoretic model predictive control (A-RAIT-MPC)

The autonomous variant eliminates the need for sequential agent coordination by replacing the explicit dependence on preceding agents' controls with learned approximations. Specifically, instead of receiving $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_k^{\text{pre}(j)}$ from agents $i \in [j - 1]$ during sequential updates (as required in (21)–(23)), each agent $j \in [m]$ uses a NN to approximate it with $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k^{\text{pre}(j)}$, as introduced in § 2.5.

Thus, the only difference being that preceding agents' controls are estimated rather than com-

Figure 4. Training the j^{th} agent to approximate $\bar{u}_k^{\text{pre}(j)}$ using a neural network equipped with a reward comparator to trigger adaptation under changing disturbance distribution.

municated, *c.f.* Fig. 3. This shift from sequential to autonomous execution removes inter-agent communication bottlenecks and enables fully decentralized and parallel action computation effectively applying u_k^{aut} on the environment similar to the sequential counterpart u_k^{seq} , significantly improving scalability and runtime efficiency in MASs.

3.5 Learning approximate agent controls

In the MA-A-RAIT-MPC framework, each agent $j \in [m]$ requires an estimate of the control inputs of preceding agents $i \in [j - 1]$ to solve its agent-centric control problem independently. To this end, a NN function $\phi^j : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{U}^{\text{prec}(j)}$, parameterized by θ^j , is trained to approximate the mapping

$$\hat{u}_k^{\text{prec}(j)} = \phi^j(\mathbf{x}_k; \bar{\theta}^j), \quad (28)$$

where $\bar{\theta}^j$ is the best parameter vector obtained by optimizing some cost function over θ^j . The cost function for training the NN model is based on a dataset \mathcal{D}^j of size D , consisting of state-control input pairs. In particular, we have

$$\mathcal{D}^j = \left\{ \left(\mathbf{x}_k^{(d)}, \bar{u}_k^{\text{prec}(j)(d)} \right) \right\}_{d=1}^D, \quad (29)$$

and is generated from past sequential MA rollout executions. The dataset may also be stored in the edge cloud so that it can be downloaded by agents whenever needed for training their NNs. It is worth noting that the dataset is collected under the distribution p_w of the disturbance. A commonly used cost function is the mean-squared error, where the parameter vector $\bar{\theta}^j$ is given

by

$$\bar{\theta}^j \in \arg \min_{\theta^j} \frac{1}{D} \sum_{d=1}^D \left\| \phi^j(\mathbf{x}_k^{(d)}; \theta^j) - \bar{\mathbf{u}}_k^{\text{prec}(j)(d)} \right\|^2. \quad (30)$$

This trained function ϕ^j replaces real-time communication in (23), allowing each agent to independently approximate the influence of others during decision-making *c.f.* Fig.4. Nonetheless, the previously collected dataset \mathcal{D}^j becomes outdated when the distribution p_w evolves rendering the model of the other agent outdated. In this respect, to yield an adaptive autonomy, first one needs to identify any changes of the distributions of the disturbances. To identify such changes, a reward comparator is deployed (*c.f.* Fig.4) to monitor the system’s performance using a moving average of collected rewards. Let R_k be the reward at time k . The moving average over a window of size W_{rew} is computed as,

$$\bar{R}_k = \frac{1}{W_{\text{rew}}} \sum_{t=k-W_{\text{rew}}+1}^k R_t. \quad (31)$$

When $R_k < \gamma \bar{R}_k$ for a fixed sensitivity threshold $\gamma \in (0, 1)$, we say that a performance degradation is detected and the current neural network ϕ^j is flagged as misaligned with the current environment (assuming there are no other factors contributing to this). This entails collection of new data \mathcal{D}^j under the new disturbance distribution so that ϕ^j is updated by retraining, to yield a new parameter vector according to (30).

3.6 Agent ordering in sequential MA rollout

The performance of sequential MA rollout depends heavily on the order in which agents are optimized. While a fixed ordering $[m] \triangleq \{1, \dots, m\}$ is commonly assumed, different strategies for determining the agent order can significantly affect the quality and efficiency of control. Three mechanisms for agent ordering are investigated in this work, each of which generates an ordering σ that is passed into the sequential rollout planner (Algorithm 2):

1. **State-Dependent Exhaustive Ordering (Algorithm 3):** At each timestep k , all $m!$ permutations of agent orderings are evaluated by invoking Algorithm 2 for each, and the ordering that yields the lowest rollout cost is selected as the best ordering best_order_k . This provides optimal ordering per state but is computationally expensive and typically requires a centralized controller.
2. **Fixed Ordering from Initial State (Algorithm 4):** A one-time exhaustive search is performed at the initial state x_0 to determine the best ordering best_order_0 , which is then reused for all subsequent time steps. Our argument here is that the initial distribution of the state has an impact on the agent ordering. This amortizes the search cost over time, but assumes that the best initial ordering remains valid across state evolution. Like the previous method, this may also assume centralized coordination.
3. **Heuristic Q-Factor-Based Ordering (Algorithm 5):** At each state x_k , each agent independently computes a local heuristic score $h(x_k, j)$ (e.g., based on expected reward). The agents are then ordered in ascending order of their scores to form σ_k . This strategy is decentralized such that agents compute scores locally, and a one-time consensus protocol can be used to agree on the final ordering across the team.

Algorithm 3 State-Dependent Exhaustive Agent Ordering

```

1: Given:  $x_k$ , current state;  $\mathcal{P}$ , all permutations of agents  $m$ 
2: Initialize  $\text{best\_cost}_k \leftarrow \infty$ ,  $\text{best\_order}_k \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3: for each permutation  $\sigma \in \mathcal{P}$  do
4:    $\text{cost}_\sigma \leftarrow \text{Algorithm2}(x_k, \sigma)$ 
5:   if  $\text{cost}_\sigma < \text{best\_cost}_k$  then
6:      $\text{best\_cost}_k \leftarrow \text{cost}_\sigma$ 
7:      $\text{best\_order}_k \leftarrow \sigma$ 
8:   end if
9: end for
10: Execute steps 2 to 18 in  $\text{Algorithm2}(x_k, \text{best\_order}_k)$  for each  $k$ 

```

Algorithm 4 Fixed Agent Ordering from Initial State

```

1: Given:  $x_0$ , initial state;  $\mathcal{P}$ , all permutations of agent indices  $[m]$ 
2: Initialize  $\text{best\_cost}_0 \leftarrow \infty$ ,  $\text{best\_order}_0 \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3: for each permutation  $\sigma \in \mathcal{P}$  do
4:    $\text{cost}_\sigma \leftarrow \text{Algorithm2}(x_0, \sigma)$ 
5:   if  $\text{cost}_\sigma < \text{best\_cost}_0$  then
6:      $\text{best\_cost}_0 \leftarrow \text{cost}_\sigma$ 
7:      $\text{best\_order}_0 \leftarrow \sigma$ 
8:   end if
9: end for
10: Execute  $\text{Algorithm2}(x_k, \text{best\_order}_0)$  for all  $k$ 

```

Algorithm 5 Heuristic Q-Factor-Based Agent Ordering

```

1: Given:  $x_k$ , current state;  $\mathcal{A} = [m]$ , set of agent indices;  $h(x_k, j)$ , heuristic Q-factor estimator for agent  $j$ 
2: Initialize  $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow []$  {Empty list to store (agent, score) pairs}
3: for each agent  $j \in \mathcal{A}$  do
4:   Compute  $\text{score}_j \leftarrow h(x_k, j)$ 
5:   Append  $(j, \text{score}_j)$  to  $\mathcal{S}$ 
6: end for
7: Get  $\mathcal{S}_{\text{sorted}}$  sorting  $\mathcal{S}$  in ascending order of  $\text{score}_j$ 
8: Execute steps 2 to 18 in  $\text{Algorithm2}(x_k, \mathcal{S}_{\text{sorted}})$  for each time  $k$ 

```

These strategies provide a spectrum of trade-offs between optimality, computational complexity, and decentralization. In particular, the heuristic-based ordering supports distributed implementation, making it well-suited for scalable MASs.

3.7 MA rollout for problems with finite state and control spaces

Note that our primary contribution is on infinite state and control space problems using the proposed IT-MPC framework. However, for the sake of completeness, an established MA rollout mechanism from [4] is formalized in Algorithm 6 that is applicable for finite control and state space settings. The procedure performs an ℓ -step LA using a decision tree constructed

Algorithm 6 Monte carlo tree search (MCTS) with ℓ -Step LA and Truncated Rollout [4]

```

1: Given:  $\mathbf{x}_k$ , current state;  $\ell$ , number of LA steps;  $T$ , rollout horizon;  $N_{mcts}$ , number of
   MC simulations;  $\mathcal{U}$ , discrete action space;  $f$ , transition model;  $g$ , stage cost function;  $g_N$ ,
   terminal cost function
2:  $k = 0$ 
3: while Task is not completed do
4:   current state =  $\mathbf{x}_k$ ;  $\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{pre}(1)} = \emptyset$ ;  $\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{seq}} = \emptyset$ 
5:   for each agent  $j \in [M]$  do
6:     Receive preceding agents' controls  $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_k^{\text{pre}(j)}$ 
7:     for  $n = 1$  to  $N_{mcts}$  do
8:       path  $\leftarrow []$ , cost  $\leftarrow 0$ ,  $\mathbf{x}_0 \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_k$ 
       {LA phase for  $\ell$  steps}
9:       for  $t = 0$  to  $\ell - 1$  do
10:        Draw decision tree by expanding  $\forall \mathbf{u}_{k+t}^j \in \mathcal{U}_k$ 
11:         $\mathbf{u}_{k+t} = (\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_{k+t}}^{\text{pre}(j)}, \mathbf{u}_{k+t}^j, \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_{k+t}}^{\text{succ}(j)})$  c.f. (32)
12:        path  $\leftarrow \text{path} \cup \{(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_{k+t})\}$ 
13:        cost  $\leftarrow \text{cost} + g(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_{k+t})$ 
14:         $\mathbf{x}_{t+1} \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t)$ 
15:       end for
       {Truncated rollout phase for  $T$  steps from  $\mathbf{x}_\ell$ }
16:       for  $t = \ell$  to  $\ell + T - 1$  do
17:        cost  $\leftarrow \text{cost} + g(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t)$  c.f. (32)
18:         $\mathbf{x}_{t+1} \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t)$ 
19:       end for
20:       cost  $\leftarrow \text{cost} + g_N(\mathbf{x}_{\ell+T})$ 
21:     end for
22:     return  $\mathbf{u}_k^j$ * corresponding to the branch at  $\mathbf{x}_k$  with the lowest average cumulative cost
23:      $\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{pre}(j+1)} \leftarrow (\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{pre}(j)}, \mathbf{u}_k^j)$ ;  $\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{seq}} \leftarrow (\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{seq}}, \mathbf{u}_k^j)$ 
24:   end for
25:    $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = f(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k^{\text{seq}}, \mathbf{w}_k)$ ;  $k = k + 1$ 
26: end while

```

over all control options at each state. For the first LA step ($t = 0$), previously communicated controls from agents 1 to $j - 1$ are used. For $t > 0$, actions for preceding and succeeding agents are generated using a base policy, BP ,

$$\mathbf{u}_{k+t} = \begin{cases} (\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_{k+t}}^{\text{pre}(j)}, \mathbf{u}_{k+t}^j, \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{x}_{k+t}}^{\text{succ}(j)}), & \text{if } t = 0, \\ (\mathbf{u}_{BP(\mathbf{x}_{k+t})}^{\text{pre}(j)}, \mathbf{u}_{k+t}^j, \mathbf{u}_{BP(\mathbf{x}_{k+t})}^{\text{succ}(j)}), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

Following the LA phase, a truncated rollout of length T is executed from the terminal node, and a terminal cost function is applied to estimate the value of the final state. The cumulative cost along the rollout, including the terminal cost, is backpropagated to all nodes in the explored path. This process is repeated across multiple MC simulations to estimate expected costs. Finally, the branch in the decision tree with the lowest estimated cumulative cost is selected, and its first control is communicated to the next agent in the sequence.

4 RESULTS

In this section, the experimental setup has been detailed, followed by the performance evaluation of the proposed S-RAIT-MPC and A-RAIT-MPC algorithms under a fixed disturbance distribution p_w . For comparison, the SOTA MADDPG algorithm has been employed as a baseline. Subsequently, a scenario has been considered where the disturbance distribution p_w , is altered mid-task, and the performance of the proposed methods has been evaluated, along with a discussion of the corrective strategies implemented to restore the system to its desired performance level. In the later part of this section, trade-off analyses of Algorithm 6 have been presented under varying parameter configurations.

4.1 Experimental setups

The proposed algorithm and associated trade-off analyses are evaluated in a simulated environment, where a MAS must collaboratively capture a set of targets by entering their vicinity. The task is considered complete once all targets are captured. The system evolves in discrete time steps indexed by k , as referenced in Algorithms 1, 2, and 6. The number of steps required to complete the task is used as the primary performance metric.

A reward signal R_k is defined as the negative number of elapsed time steps, i.e., $R_k = -k$. Due to the homogeneous nature of agents and the collaborative objective, rewards are not assigned individually. Such agent specific reward shaping is beyond the scope of this work, hence, R_k serves directly as a higher-is-better performance measure. Algorithms 1, 2, and 6 aims to direct the agents toward task completion, while the behavior of the targets is governed by a disturbance distribution p_w , which constitutes both their initial placement and movement throughout the task. Agents are indexed from 1 to m . Targets are indexed from 1 to n .

The evaluation environments are categorized into two settings: *continuous* and *discrete*. In the continuous setting, we employ the multi particle environments (MPE) simulation environment described in [39], which models a two-dimensional domain as a square region with both width and height equal to L , allowing agents and targets to move freely in any direction, *c.f.* Fig. 5(a). In contrast, the discrete setting uses an $L \times L$ square grid environment from [4], where the movements of agents and targets are constrained by the grid structure, *c.f.* Fig. 5(b). Consequently, the state space for the continuous setting, denoted $\mathcal{X}_{\text{cont}}$ is the $2mn$ dimensional box given by

$$\mathcal{X}_{\text{cont}} = \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{2mn} \mid \mathbf{0} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq L\mathbf{1}\}, \quad (33)$$

where $\mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{1}$ denote vectors whose components are all zeros and ones, respectively, with dimensions determined by context. Moreover, the state space \mathcal{X}_{dis} in the discrete setting is simply given by

$$\mathcal{X}_{\text{dis}} = \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{Z}^{2mn} \mid \mathbf{0} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq L\mathbf{1}\}. \quad (34)$$

In either setting, the state is based on the positions of agents and the targets. More specifically, let $\mathbf{a}_k^j \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denote the position of agent j at time k and $\mathbf{b}_k^i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denote the position of target i at time k . Thus, at time step k , the system state vector $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{2mn}$ is defined by,

$$\mathbf{x}_k = (\mathbf{a}_k, \mathbf{b}_k), \quad (35)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_k = (\mathbf{a}_k^1, \dots, \mathbf{a}_k^m) \in \mathbb{R}^{2m}$ and $\mathbf{b}_k = (\mathbf{b}_k^1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_k^n) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$.

The continuous setting, considered for evaluating A-RAIT-MPC and S-RAIT-MPC, features both continuous state and action spaces. According to the environment described in [39], there are 5 components associated with the action of each agent j and are denoted by $(u_{c\text{-idle}}^j, u_{c\text{-up}}^j, u_{c\text{-down}}^j, u_{c\text{-left}}^j, u_{c\text{-right}}^j) \in [0, \alpha]^5$ for some $\alpha > 0$, where ‘c-’ is used to signify the continuous setting. However, to remain consistent with our mathematical formulation, the action space for agent j is equivalently defined as ¹

$$\mathcal{U}_{\text{cont}}^j(\mathbf{x}) = \left\{ \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid \mathbf{u} = \left(u_{c\text{-right}}^j - u_{c\text{-left}}^j, u_{c\text{-up}}^j - u_{c\text{-down}}^j \right), -\alpha \mathbf{1} \leq \mathbf{u} \leq \alpha \mathbf{1} \right\}. \quad (36)$$

Unless stated otherwise, $\alpha = 1$ in all experiments.

The discrete setting, used in the evaluation and trade-off analysis of Algorithm 6, employs discrete actions. In particular, as specified in the considered environment [4], the action of each agent j consists of five components $(u_{d\text{-idle}}^j, u_{d\text{-up}}^j, u_{d\text{-down}}^j, u_{d\text{-left}}^j, u_{d\text{-right}}^j) \in \{0, 1, \dots, \beta\}^5$ for some positive integer β , where we use ‘d-’ to indicate that the setting is discrete. Consequently, the action space for agent j is given by

$$\mathcal{U}_{\text{dis}}^j(\mathbf{x}) = \left\{ \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \mid \mathbf{u} = \left(u_{d\text{-right}}^j - u_{d\text{-left}}^j, u_{d\text{-up}}^j - u_{d\text{-down}}^j \right), -\beta \mathbf{1} \leq \mathbf{u} \leq \beta \mathbf{1} \right\}. \quad (37)$$

In our experiments we set $\beta = 1$ unless specified otherwise. Similarly to the continuous setting, the set above is clipped accordingly to prevent agents from exiting the state space.

In continuous and discrete settings, a random vector $\mathbf{w}_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is chosen as the disturbance with a given probability distributions p_{c-w} and p_{d-w} , respectively. Thus the transition model f is affine and is characterized by

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_{k+1} \\ \mathbf{b}_{k+1} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{x}_{k+1}} = f(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{w}_k) \triangleq \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_k \\ \mathbf{b}_k \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{x}_k} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_k \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{w}_k \end{bmatrix},$$

where \mathbf{u}_k is either an element of $\mathcal{U}_{\text{cont}}^1(\mathbf{x}_k) \times \dots \times \mathcal{U}_{\text{cont}}^m(\mathbf{x}_k)$ or $\mathcal{U}_{\text{dis}}^1(\mathbf{x}_k) \times \dots \times \mathcal{U}_{\text{dis}}^m(\mathbf{x}_k)$, depending on the setting.

The base policies used in the continuous setting, denoted as BP_{roll} and BP_{mpc} , operates over a continuous action space by computing the Euclidean distance to the nearest target and scaling the resulting vector to lie within the admissible control bounds of the action space. For the discrete setting, the BP computes the Manhattan distance to the closest target and selects a direction that advances the agent along the corresponding Manhattan grid-aligned path. A summary of parameters used in the experimental setup is provided in Table 1. Fig. 5 illustrates the simulated environments, with annotated action-spaces and BP behaviors.

For the continuous setting the terminal cost function d_τ for each trajectory $\tau \in [M]$ is found by the average Euclidean distance to uncaptured targets at the terminal state $\mathbf{x}_{k+\ell+T,i}$ given by,

$$d_i = \frac{1}{m \cdot |\bar{\mathcal{T}}|} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j \in \bar{\mathcal{T}}} \left\| \mathbf{a}_k^j - \mathbf{b}_k^j \right\|_2, \quad (38)$$

¹Although not explicitly specified for notational convenience, when \mathbf{x} is sufficiently close to the boundary of $\mathcal{X}_{\text{cont}}$, $\mathcal{U}_{\text{cont}}^j(\mathbf{x})$ is straightforwardly clipped to ensure that the agents do not move beyond the set $\mathcal{X}_{\text{cont}}$.

Table 1. Parameters of the experimental environments.

Property	Value	
	Continuous setting	Discrete setting
Number of agents: m	2	2, 3, 4, 5
Number of targets: n	2	2
State space: \mathcal{X}	$\mathcal{X}_{\text{cont}}$	\mathcal{X}_{dis}
Action space of agent j : \mathcal{U}^j	$\mathcal{U}_{\text{cont}}^j(\mathbf{x})$	$\mathcal{U}_{\text{dis}}^j(\mathbf{x})$
Base policy	Euclidean distance	Manhattan distance
Target capture criterion	$\ \mathbf{a}_k^j - \mathbf{b}_k^j\ _2 \leq r_{cv}$	$\mathbf{a}_k^j = \mathbf{b}_k^j$
Terminal cost function	<i>c.f.</i> (38)	<i>c.f.</i> (39)

Figure 5. Screenshots of target capture evaluation environments of size $L \times L$ with agents marked in green circles and targets marked in red circles. (a) Continuous setting with $m = 2$, $n = 2$; (b) Discrete setting with $L = 10$, $m = 3$, $n = 2$.

and for the discrete setting the terminal cost function g_N is found by the average Manhattan distance to uncaptured targets at the terminal state given by,

$$g_N = \frac{1}{m \cdot |\bar{\mathcal{T}}|} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j \in \bar{\mathcal{T}}} \|\mathbf{a}_k^j - \mathbf{b}_k^j\|_1, \quad (39)$$

where $\bar{\mathcal{T}} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ is the set of uncaptured targets as of the terminal state.

4.2 Performance evaluation of MA-S-RAIT-MPC and MA-A-RAIT-MPC

This section presents the evaluation of the proposed MA-S-RAIT-MPC and MA-A-RAIT-MPC algorithms under a fixed disturbance distribution. Performance is compared against two baselines: (1) a BP where each agent moves toward the nearest target using Euclidean distance, and (2) the MADDPG algorithm. For both proposed methods, the horizon length T of BP_{roll} is varied while maintaining a one-step LA ($\ell = 1$). Higher values of ℓ are beyond the scope of this thesis and are discussed as future directions in §5.

Table 2. Number of offline training samples required by different methods.

Method	Training Samples Needed
MA-S-RAIT-MPC	0
MA-A-RAIT-MPC	50,000
MADDPG	80,000

For the MADDPG implementation, each agent is equipped with a parameterized actor–critic pair. The actor network consists of two fully connected hidden layers with 64 ReLU units each and is optimized using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.01. The critic network also comprises two hidden layers of 64 ReLU units, followed by a linear output layer producing a scalar Q -value. It was trained by minimizing the mean squared Bellman error using Adam with a learning rate of 0.01. A discount factor of 0.95 is used for future rewards, and the target networks are updated using soft updates with an interpolation coefficient of 0.01.

Figs. 6 and 7 show that increasing the horizon improves the mean rewards for both MA-S-RAIT-MPC and MA-A-RAIT-MPC, though at the cost of increased computation. The rate of reward improvement diminishes at larger horizons, indicating a trade-off between planning depth and computational overhead. The key difference between the two proposed methods lies in how agents obtain the actions of their predecessors. In MA-S-RAIT-MPC, agents receive preceding actions $\mathbf{u}_k^{\text{pre}(j)}$ through perfect communication. In contrast, MA-A-RAIT-MPC relies on predicting preceding actions $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k^{\text{pre}(j)}$ using a neural classifier (Fig. 4). As a result, MA-A-RAIT-MPC consistently shows slightly lower mean rewards. More sophisticated prediction models could potentially bridge this performance gap, which is left for future exploration.

Compared to the BP, both proposed methods achieve higher mean rewards, confirming their effectiveness in cost minimization. Although MADDPG achieves superior mean reward and runtime, this performance depends heavily on extensive offline training with large datasets. Table 2 shows that MA-S-RAIT-MPC requires no offline training, while MA-A-RAIT-MPC uses fewer samples than MADDPG to learn predictions of preceding actions $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k^{\text{pre}(j)}$ and perform the task online. Unlike MADDPG, the proposed rollout-based methods offer interpretable and verifiable decisions through explicit planning. They are less reliant on large datasets, complex architectures, and sensitive hyperparameter tuning. Furthermore, MADDPG exhibits greater relative-performance degradation under changes in the disturbance distribution, as shown in Fig. 8 and further discussed in §4.3.

4.3 Evaluation under changing disturbance distributions

The evaluation of the performance of MA-A-RAIT-MPC when the disturbance distribution is changed mid-task is presented here. Initially, each target samples its actions from a structured, multimodal Gaussian distribution, where the mean vector alternates based on the target’s index. After a fixed number of steps, this distribution is abruptly switched to a uniform distribution over the action space. This shift alters the behavioral patterns of the targets, invalidating the models of the preceding previously learned by the successive agents. The following analysis demonstrates how the MA-A-RAIT-MPC respond to this distributional shift and highlights their ability in adapting online compared to the MADDPG baseline.

Fig. 8 presents four performance curves corresponding to the collected mean reward. Three of them are under various lengths of the horizon $T = \{0, 5, 30\}$ while retraining the invalid prediction model with collected valid samples. When agents do not update their models of preceding agents, performance initially drops due to the model mismatch. However, the impact

Figure 6. Mean reward comparison with increasing length of the horizon T of BP_{roll} with $\ell = 1$

Table 3. Worst case MA-A-RAIT-MPC performance degradation and recovery comparison.

Method	Mean Reward Drop (%)	Recovery Steps ($\times 100$)
MADDPG	57.14%	810
MA-A-RAIT-MPC ($T = 0$)	22.22%	420

of this degradation depends on the configuration of the T . Recall that the proposed method integrates three components: multi-step LA (ℓ), truncated rollout of length T and a terminal cost approximation d . When $T = 0$, the terminal cost relies entirely on a heuristic approximation, i.e., the average distance between each predator and the remaining prey. In this setting, model adaptation becomes essential for performance recovery, and retraining the NNs eventually restores effectiveness. With a short rollout horizon ($T = 5$), some tasks are already completed during the rollout, reducing the average reliance on the terminal cost estimate. Consequently, the performance drop is smaller, and recovery via model adaptation is faster. In contrast, for a longer rollout horizon ($T = 30$), most tasks are completed within the truncated rollout itself, rendering the terminal cost estimate nearly irrelevant. Notably, in this case, performance remains robust without any model updates, illustrating the inherent resilience of the system to environmental changes when deep planning is employed with the trade-off of higher computational load as presented in Fig. 7.

Even though MADDPG showed far superior performance as shown in Fig. 6 and 7, it shows far worse percentage drop of performance when met with changing disturbances of the system. As presented in Table 3 it takes 92% longer to get back to normality compared to that of the worst case performance of MA-A-RAIT-MPC. It is also noteworthy that for MADDPG even to reach the normality performance of MA-A-RAIT-MPC it takes approximately 23% longer. This reiterates the simplicity and the resiliency of the proposed MA-A-RAIT-MPC as an online algorithm.

Figure 7. Mean run time comparison with increasing length of the horizon T of BP_{roll} with $\ell = 1$

4.4 Evaluating optimization of agents order

This section presents an evaluation of agent ordering strategies, namely the default ordering $[m]$, the optimized ordering strategy described in Algorithm 4, and the heuristic-based ordering strategy from Algorithm 5 in the context of the discrete-action counterpart of MA-S-RAIT-MPC (Algorithm 6). The goal is to assess how different ordering strategies affect task performance in terms of mean reward and task completion time, which includes inter-agent communication latency.

Fig. 9a plots the collected mean reward for each agent ordering mechanism as the number of agents m increases, while holding the task difficulty constant (i.e., number of targets fixed at $n = 2$). Corresponding task completion times are shown in Fig. 9b on a logarithmic scale. The results demonstrate that the optimized ordering consistently leads to higher rewards compared to the default ordering, with the performance gap widening as the number of agents increases. This supports the hypothesis that initial agent-target placement assignments significantly influence overall coordination efficiency in the MAS evaluated in this work.

Although the optimized ordering (Algorithm 4) achieves the best reward outcomes, it incurs the highest runtime due to the factorial search space of agent permutations ($m!$), even when evaluated in parallel. In contrast, the heuristic-based ordering (Algorithm 5) achieves nearly comparable rewards with substantially less computational cost. Interestingly, its runtime decreases with increasing m , as the larger agent pool facilitates quicker task resolution for a fixed number of targets. Conversely, the default ordering not only underperforms in reward collection but also exhibits increasing task completion time as the number of agents grows. This trend further emphasizes the benefits of incorporating intelligent ordering strategies, even heuristic ones, to enhance coordination efficiency in MASs.

Figure 8. Effect of truncated rollout length T on adaptation performance under changing disturbance distribution. Longer rollouts (higher T) reduce reliance on learned models and improve resilience to distributional shifts in p_w , while shorter rollouts (lower T) require model adaptation to recover performance.

4.5 Performance under varying number of MC simulations

This section evaluates the effect of varying the number of MC simulations (N_{mcts}) and the number of agents ($m = 2, 3, 4, 5$) in the system on overall performance and computational efficiency, while maintaining a fixed task difficulty (i.e., number of targets $n = 2$). Specifically, the system’s performance is assessed in terms of the mean reward collected and the time required to complete the task. Comparisons are made between a uniform allocation of MC simulations across agents and configurations where the total number of simulations varies with the number of agents.

Fig. 10 can be analyzed by dividing it to low MC budget regime (LMCBR) where $N_{mcts} < 20$ and high MC budget regime (HMCBR) where $N_{mcts} > 20$. In the LMCBR, reward collected by the MAS is sensitive to increasing N_{mcts} compared to that of HMCBR. Additionally, adding more agents enhances performance in LMCBR, but this benefit diminishes as the system configuration moves toward HMCBR where m does not have much effect on the rewards collected. Importantly, in the HMCBR, runtime begins to increase steeply. This sharp rise in computational cost highlights a critical trade-off between performance gains and real-time feasibility. The identification of such a threshold (e.g. $N_{mcts} = 20$) is particularly valuable for cooperative MAS design, where balancing task efficiency with runtime constraints is essential.

A key observation from Fig. 11 is the strong inverse relationship between N_{mcts} and variance of reward collected. As N_{mcts} increases, the variance in reward across experiment runs drops significantly for all m configurations, indicating increased stability. However, this reduction in variance is more pronounced in smaller teams. For larger numbers of agents, the rate at which variance decreases with additional simulations is lower. These findings establish a clear baseline for how simulation budget and N_{mcts} affects performance, stability, and computational cost, providing context for the adaptive allocation strategies explored in the next section.

Figure 9. Performance variation observed with reordering agents in Algorithm 6 a) Mean reward and b) Run time.

Figure 10. Reward and run time comparison with N_{mcts} for team configurations

4.6 Prioritized sampling: adaptive number of MC simulations allocation strategy

Building on the findings from the previous section, which evaluated the system's performance under varying but uniform MC simulation budgets across all agents, now a more dynamic strategy is considered where allocating a different number of simulations to each agent based on its individual decision context. The motivation stems from the observation that while increasing the total number of MC simulations generally improves performance, uniform allocation may not be the most efficient use of computational resources. In many MA scenarios, agents are not equally critical in every state. Some may have more influence over the system's near-term trajectory than others. Exploiting this asymmetry, an adaptive MC allocation mechanism is proposed where the number of simulations per agent is modulated according to a state-dependent quality metric.

Figure 11. Variance of rewards collected vs. N_{mcts} for team configurations

Figure 12. Performance comparison with different adaptation schemes for $m = 4$ and $n = 2$

To this end, a heuristic Q-factor (Q_i) for each agent is computed at each time step k as,

$$Q_i = \frac{1}{|\bar{\mathcal{T}}|} \sum_{j \in \bar{\mathcal{T}}} |a_k^j - b_k^j|_1, \quad (40)$$

where $\bar{\mathcal{T}} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ denotes the set of uncaptured targets at time step k capturing the expected value or contribution of that agent's decision in its current state. Using this Q-factor, per-agent-simulation-numbers (N_{mcts}^i) are allocated via several functions that adaptively decide the value for N_{mcts}^i based on Q_i within a given budget.

It is found that, as shown in Fig. 12, monotonically increasing functions with respect to the Q-factor (e.g., x , x^2 , e^x) consistently yield better task performance and lower run times compared to both uniform allocation and decreasing functions (e.g., x^{-1} , $-x$), which tend to under-allocate resources to high-impact decisions. Among the strategies tested, exponential growth functions strike the best trade-off, due to the enabling of deeper planning by allocating higher N_{mcts}^i

Figure 13. N-Step LA comparison of reward and time with N_{mcts} for a MAS with $m = 4$ and $n = 2$ a) Mean reward and b) Run time.

for agents producing high Q-factor, in other words where it matters most without unnecessary overhead elsewhere.

These results demonstrate that adaptive allocation offers a principled and effective mechanism for prioritizing computational effort in rollout-based MA planning, especially when operating under resource constraints or in scenarios with heterogeneous agent influence.

4.7 Evaluating the balance between LA depth, N_{mcts} and run time

Analysis on the effect of increasing ℓ in Algorithm 6 on collected reward and task execution run time is presented in this section. Upon initially hypothesizing that for a fixed number of agents and a constant task difficulty (fixed n), enforcing deeper LA by incorporating higher ℓ values improves performance by enabling more informed decisions, albeit at the cost of increased computational overhead, the following observation has been made.

Experimental results shown in Fig. 13 validate this hypothesis. As the LA depth increases, cumulative reward improves, indicating more effective planning. However, when pairing higher number of N_{mcts} with higher ℓ , the marginal gains diminish due to immediate next ℓ steps are chosen in a cost effective manner. These findings highlight a fundamental trade-off between planning depth and computational feasibility. When run time or resource constraints are a concern, allocating budget to increase N_{mcts} , rather than expanding the LA depth may yield better overall task efficiency. This insight is especially relevant for online MAS operating in dynamic environments, where timely decisions are critical.

5 SUMMARY AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This thesis presented a novel framework that integrates MA rollout algorithms with IT-MPC to address complex multistage decision problems. The proposed approach supports both sequential and autonomous coordination strategies, enabling scalable and efficient decentralized decision-making across agents operating in continuous state and action spaces. Systematic evaluations were presented on the impact of various algorithmic design choices, including agent ordering, simulation budgets, rollout depth, and adaptive simulation allocation. Presented results demonstrated significant gains in task efficiency, robustness to dynamic environments, and reduced computational overhead compared to baseline and SOTA RL methods. Notably, adaptive mechanisms such as prioritized simulation budgeting and heuristic-based ordering that provide practical pathways for real-time planning in resource-constrained scenarios.

In real-world applications, continuous or infinite control and state spaces are prevalent, prompting the key question, *can rollout algorithms be practically deployed for such problems?*. This thesis addresses it by integrating rollout planning with the IT-MPC framework. Each agent independently performs online LA simulations, enabling local rollout-based policy improvements resembling distributed RL. This RAIT-MPC framework combines decentralized planning with MPC, allowing agents to anticipate future interactions while maintaining coordinated group behavior. For the development of A-RAIT-MPC more sophisticated methods of modeling of other agents could be explored as potential future avenues.

Traditional computation offloading and mobility management strategies fail under connectivity loss or contention spikes. In the RAIT-MPC presented in this thesis, each agent conducts MC simulations over its control horizon, using lightweight base policies (for continuous actions) or MCTS (for discrete actions) to estimate rollout costs. Agents anticipate downstream consequences by simulating interactions under assumed behavior models, reducing the risk of cascading failures. Further work can be extended using partial observations by each agent and exchange concise statistics among the team rather than full trajectories, blending autonomy with occasional global coordination.

Communication optimization in MAS has been an active area of research. Early efforts focused on predefined task-specific protocols, such as directing swarm robots by transmitting nearest-target information [40]. These methods handled challenges of non-homogeneity and partial observability. When tasks are dynamic or partially known, protocols communicating meta-level task information (e.g., actuator activations in vehicles [41]) proved more robust.

The proposed framework aligns with theoretical developments in [36] and ensures that edge devices such as drones, sensors, or vehicles can make near-optimal decisions independently, even without continuous cloud connectivity. Beyond application value, the framework is motivated by two critical issues: (i) intermittent connectivity forcing high energy expenditures for communication, and (ii) systemic risks from uncoordinated failures in large-scale IoT deployments. Historical engineering failures highlight the importance of proactively addressing adaptive behaviors in interconnected systems. Vaughan [42] links the Challenger disaster to the normalization of deviance. Other cases such as Boeing 737 MAX crashes [43], software race conditions in radiation therapy machines [44], decentralized failures in the Northeast black-out [45], and algorithmic stock market losses [46] underline the need for systems that can adapt to unseen disturbances. When the distribution of the disturbance changes, agents can leverage past knowledge and incorporate continuous-learning [47, 48] strategies rather than retraining from the beginning that could further improve the resiliency of the MAS.

Recent approaches shift towards agents learning their own communication protocols. Kasai et al.[49] show agents developing their own codewords, trading off communication efficiency and learning cost. Other works demonstrated emergent languages in cooperative guessing games

using differentiable inter-agent learning[50, 51, 52], relying on centralized training with discrete messaging during decentralized execution. Further research work can be continued following the work produced in this thesis on how the communication can be scaled effectively. There may be cases when some agents may not have an impact on the others which raises the question: *is it worth maintaining a communication channel with that agent?*.

Beyond communication, adaptation and system resilience have been key research focuses. Although *intelligence* and *adaptation* are often used interchangeably in AI literature, adaptation fundamentally involves optimizing actions in response to environmental changes [53]. Decades of research have explored adaptive agent collaboration, including Stanford's computer-animated theater demonstrating real-time emotional adaptation [54]. Modern large language models (LLMs) exhibit similar improvisational capabilities [55]. Adaptation is crucial both for internal adjustments such as managing vehicle states during dynamic highway scenarios [56] and for updating models of other agents. [57] shows that in predator-prey simulations, agents benefit from adaptive modeling of others via case based learning (CBL), although CBL's static library limits future-proofing.

This presented work has shown promising avenues in this domain where similar results seen in TD-Backgammon producing better results with truncated rollout compared to no rollout, the MAS driven by IT-MPC augmented rollout showed higher resiliency for system disturbances with truncated rollout. This is an exciting observation worth exploring further with partial observability and with competing agents driven by self-play. Extending this further to understand the features of the disturbance distributions that create such an inherent resiliency is an interesting research avenue to explore.

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